

Adaptive Inter CU Partitioning Based on a Look-Ahead Stage for HEVC

Gabriel Cebrián-Márquez^{a,*}, José Luis Martínez^b, Pedro Cuenca^b

^aDepartment of Computer Science, University of Oviedo, C/ Federico Garca Lorca 18, 33007, Oviedo, Spain

^bDepartment of Computer Science, University of Castilla-La Mancha, Campus Universitario s/n, 02071, Albacete, Spain

Abstract

High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) has become the state-of-the-art video coding standard. It outperforms its predecessors by the introduction of new coding tools, such as the new quadtree-based partitioning scheme called the coding tree unit (CTU), which enables a more flexible partitioning of the input frames. However, selecting the optimal partitioning requires the evaluation of numerous possibilities, which involves long computing times that hinder the applicability of the standard in real-world scenarios. With this in mind, the main focus of this paper is on tackling this complexity by means of a fast partitioning and mode decision algorithm based on a look-ahead stage. This stage performs a preliminary motion estimation that provides the motion costs used to build the least-cost quadtree, which is in turn utilized to conduct the encoding itself. On the basis of this quadtree, the encoder may decide to terminate the partitioning early, or to evaluate additional depth levels adaptively. Furthermore, the encoder may omit some prediction modes according to the costs estimated by the look-ahead stage. A thorough experimental evaluation of the algorithm shows that it can reduce the encoding time by 65.33%, at the expense of only a 1.35% BD-rate for the random access configuration. Combined with a fast inter prediction algorithm, this reduction can rise to 70.55%, while the coding efficiency is maintained at a 1.83% BD-rate. When compared with other related works, these results display an excellent trade-off between the two variables.

Keywords: HEVC, fast encoding, pre-analysis, partitioning, mode decision, inter prediction

1. Introduction

Over the last decade, there has been a marked increase in the demand for a better quality of experience with multimedia contents. The growing popularity of high-definition video, and the advent of new formats such as 4k and 8k has motivated research into novel coding tools that improve the coding efficiency of state-of-the-art standards. Moreover, the traffic generated by video-on-demand services is imposing severe strain on communication networks. As a way to address these demands, the ITU-T Video Coding Experts Group (VCEG) and the ISO/IEC Moving Picture Experts Group (MPEG) organizations developed the High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) standard, as part of the Joint Collaborative Team on Video Coding (JCT-VC) [1]. The first version of the standard was released in early 2013, but several revisions have been published since then to support additional application scenarios, such as range extensions with enhanced precision and color format support, multiview and 3D, scalable coding, and screen content coding.

The new HEVC standard is usually considered as the evolution of its predecessor, namely H.264/MPEG-4 Advanced Video Coding (AVC) [2]. Content providers and manufacturers adopted H.264/MPEG-4 AVC in countless scenarios because of its good coding efficiency, displacing older standards within their existing application domains [3]. Nevertheless, all

the aforementioned demands for improved coding efficiency, higher quality and new video formats motivated the development of HEVC. In this way, in addition to addressing these demands, this standard is able to achieve a 35.4% bitrate saving on average for an equal peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR), or around a 50% bitrate saving based on subjective quality assessments compared with H.264/MPEG-4 AVC [4]. This improved performance has attracted the attention of a large number of companies, which already implement this standard in many of their products.

Among all the encoding tools introduced in HEVC, it is worth highlighting the new block-based hierarchical structure into which pictures are partitioned. This structure, called the coding tree unit (CTU), can be subsequently divided into coding units (CUs), and these into prediction units (PUs) and transform units (TUs). As a result, the standard is highly adaptable to the features of the picture, which leads to better coding efficiency. Nevertheless, the process of determining the best frame partitioning requires evaluating a large number of possibilities. Consequently, the computational complexity of HEVC has increased considerably with respect to prior standards, becoming one of the most significant constraints on the implementation of this standard on current devices [5].

The optimal partitioning of a frame is determined via two main processes: CTU/CU splitting, and the mode decision. In the former, the encoder needs to identify the partitioning quadtree that provides the highest coding efficiency. This is usually accomplished by following a top-down strategy in which at each depth level it is necessary to decide whether to

*Corresponding author

Email addresses: cebriangabriel@uniovi.es

(Gabriel Cebrián-Márquez), JoseLuis.Martinez@uclm.es

(José Luis Martínez), Pedro.Cuenca@uclm.es (Pedro Cuenca)

Figure 1: Average time profile using RA configuration.

split the corresponding CU. In the latter process, once the CTU structure has been determined, each CU is assigned a prediction mode and a PU scheme, minimizing the residual generated and the bits required to signal the block. The process of finding the optimal partitioning and prediction mode is usually called rate-distortion (R-D) optimization.

As an example of the complexity introduced by this standard, Fig. 1 shows the average time distribution of a typical HEVC encoder. For this profile, the HEVC Test Model (HM) 16.6 reference software [6] was executed using Random Access (RA) configuration, quantization parameters (QPs) 22, 27, 32 and 37, and the test sequences established by the JCT-VC [7]. As can be seen, the greatest complexity lies in the selection of the optimal prediction mode for a given PU, and its subsequent transform and quantization, especially in the case of inter prediction. As a result, 10 seconds of a 1080p60 sequence can take up to approximately 17 hours to encode in a regular CPU for QP 22, which is intractable in many scenarios.

In view of this complexity, it seems clear that omitting the evaluation of CUs and PUs that do not provide optimal R-D results entails a significant reduction of the total encoding time. With this in mind, a previous work of the authors proposed a motion-based partitioning and mode decision algorithm [8]. On the basis of the preliminary information provided by a pre-analysis stage, the encoder estimates the optimal partitioning, which is used to conduct the encoding by following a set of static rules. Building on this pre-analysis stage, in this paper we present a novel adaptive algorithm that carries out the evaluation of CUs and PUs dynamically, breaking with the traditional top-down approach. As a result, the proposed scheme achieves a significant improvement in coding efficiency compared with our previous work, in addition to a small increase in terms of time reduction. Therefore, the main aim pursued by this algorithm is to enable the feasibility of HEVC in real-time scenarios while also maintaining its coding efficiency.

The aforementioned pre-analysis stage, also called look-ahead, pre-processes the input frames to obtain valuable motion information for the encoding, as shown in Fig. 2. In particular, this stage performs a fast motion estimation (ME) that calculates the distortion cost and a motion vector (MV) for each reference frame and each square block into which the pictures are divided. This information enables the building of the least-cost

Figure 2: Typical HEVC encoder architecture with a look-ahead stage.

partitioning tree, which is utilized to conduct CTU/CU splitting. In this way, this paper proposes a new evaluation process that begins with the estimated quadtree, omitting all the CUs at higher and lower depth levels. As a result, the partitioning that is most likely to provide the optimal R-D results is evaluated first. From this point forward, the proposed algorithm can terminate the CTU early, or it can adaptively evaluate additional CUs at other depth levels according to certain rules. In addition to these splitting capabilities, the proposed algorithm can also omit the evaluation of certain PUs that are unlikely to provide better R-D results than the current best. As a result, the total encoding time is significantly reduced at the expense of imperceptible coding efficiency losses compared with our previous work and a large number of related works.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 contains a thorough analysis of the most relevant related works in this field. The proposed splitting and mode decision algorithm, which is based on a look-ahead stage, is described in Section 3. An experimental evaluation is presented in Section 4, and Section 5 provides an in-depth comparison of the proposal with respect to the related works. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 6.

2. Related Work on Fast Encoding

Fast encoding has always been a popular issue in the field of HEVC. Many approaches have been adopted to reduce the total encoding time of the standard. In particular, CTU/CU splitting and the mode decision are the processes that have most frequently been addressed due to the large time savings that can

be obtained as a result. This section will highlight the most relevant works related to fast encoding methods. For this purpose, these have been classified according to the method proposed, beginning with those that only address the CTU/CU splitting decision, and followed by others that also take into consideration fast prediction methods, early skip detection schemes, and mode selection algorithms.

2.1. CTU/CU Splitting

According to statistical analyses, the partitionings of neighboring CTUs usually correlate. For this reason, many authors have studied the way to estimate the partitioning from previously coded blocks. For example, *Q. Zhang et al.* based their method on spatial and temporal neighboring information to classify the CUs into simple, normal, and complex, which enables the determination of the minimum and maximum depth levels for a CTU [9]. Similarly, the algorithm proposed by *Z. Pan et al.* limits the partitioning to depths 0 or 2 in accordance with statistics obtained from the neighbors [10]. *Y. Gao et al.* established the relationship between the least frequently used CU sizes and the QP, building a model which enables the omission of certain partitions based on the encoding information for previous groups of pictures (GOPs) [11].

On the basis of observation, many authors found a relationship between the features of the pictures and the coding parameters, and the splitting decisions. In this way, many works exploit this relationship to find the optimal CTU partitioning. *T.-L. Lin et al.* proposed an early CU termination algorithm based on the residual statistics of the current CU and the skip information of the neighbors [12]. The residual is also exploited by *H.-L. Tan et al.* in their work [13]. With regard to inter prediction, *J. Xiong et al.* proposed a splitting decision method based on the existing MV divergence in a CU [14]. Later, the same authors modeled this as a Markov random field inference problem, optimized by a graph cut algorithm [15]. *J. Liu et al.* based the splitting decision on the existence of non-zero coefficients after the transform, and also on spatial and temporal depth information, or gradients when the neighbors are not available or do not correlate [16]. Similarly, the method proposed by *Y. Li et al.* also bases the splitting decision on the existence of non-zero coefficients after the transform, and the maximum depth of temporally co-located CTUs [17]. Finally, some authors perform an analysis of the input pictures, such as *D. G. Fernández et al.*, who proposed an early termination algorithm based on the spatial and temporal homogeneity of the images [18].

The search for the optimal partitioning has also been considered as a classification problem. In this regard, the use of data mining techniques is present in many fast encoding methods. For instance, the early CU termination algorithm proposed by *G. Corrêa et al.* is based on classification trees [19]. In a similar way, *M. Grellert et al.* proposed an analogous scheme based on support vector machines [20]. *K. Kim and W. W. Ro* made use of machine learning techniques, in particular those based on neural networks (NNs), for the same purpose [21]. However, these types of algorithms require evaluating unnecessary depth levels until it is decided to stop splitting. As a way to solve this, the algorithm proposed by *Y. Zhang et al.* enables the

selection of a specific depth level by means of a joint classifier composed of multiple binary classifiers with different parameters for each depth, together with an R-D model to determine these parameters [22]. The algorithm proposed by *M. Xu et al.*, in turn, calculates the optimal CTU/CU partitioning on the basis of convolutional NNs (CNNs) and long- and short-term memory (LSTM) networks [23]. To overcome the disadvantages of the static models, *H.-S. Kim and R.-H. Park* proposed the use of Bayesian rules for on-line and off-line training with scene change detection [24]. With the same aim in mind, *H. Amer et al.* made use of fully connected NNs and Laplacian transparent composite models [25]. Similarly, *S. Momcilovic et al.* also avoided the requirement of prior training by using NNs [26].

In contrast to these works, different approaches include, for example, the complexity control algorithm proposed by *A. Jiménez-Moreno et al.* and which is based on a hierarchical approach, which makes it possible to parametrize the encoding to choose the desired complexity [27].

2.2. CTU/CU Splitting and Inter/Intra Prediction

Pruning the partitioning tree results in significant time savings. Nevertheless, the encoder still needs to perform both the inter and the intra prediction to select the optimal prediction mode. As a consequence, many authors complemented CTU/CU splitting with fast prediction algorithms. For instance, the algorithm proposed by *S. Wang et al.* performs the splitting decision based on thresholds with respect to the R-D cost of each CU [28]. It reduces the number of intra candidates by means of gradients, and also reduces the number of reference frames to be checked. The method proposed by *H. Kibeya et al.* is based on the early detection of the residual matrices that after transformation and quantization result in zero coefficients, so that CTU/CU splitting and the ME are terminated early [29]. Also related to inter prediction, *T. Mallikarachchi et al.* introduced two classification models based on the inter $N \times N$ costs to estimate the partitioning, enabling the reuse of motion vectors [30].

2.3. CTU/CU Splitting and Early Skip Detection

The use of fast prediction algorithms has numerous advantages in terms of reduction of the encoding time, but it does not solve the problem of evaluating unnecessary prediction modes. Taking into consideration the frequent use of the skip mode, in particular for low rate encodings, a different approach is to detect the use of this mode in an early stage, enabling the omission of the remaining modes for a CU. In this way, *S. Ahn et al.* made use of spatial and temporal parameters in their skip detection method and CTU/CU splitting decision algorithm, namely the sample adaptive offset (SAO) parameters, MVs, TU sizes, and the existence of non-zero coefficients [31]. As a different approach, *M. Tang et al.* proposed the reordering of the prediction modes, so first the merge/skip and the $2N \times 2N$ modes are evaluated, then the child CUs, and finally the remaining prediction modes of the current CU [32]. In this way, it is possible to prune the quadtree or perform early skip detection.

As mentioned above, the use of machine learning techniques is always present in this type of algorithms. For example, *J. Lee*

et al. defined a set of Bayesian rules based on thresholds with three main objectives: as a way to omit large CUs, to early terminate CTU/CU partitioning, and to define an early skip detection method [33]. Similarly, *J. Zhang et al.* classified the CUs into three categories with the use of Bayesian rules and the merge R-D cost, enabling their early pruning or an early detection of the skip mode [34]. For those CUs in which it is not possible to make a decision, and for I slices, the authors used conditional random fields.

Finally, it may be worth mentioning the extension made by *J. Xiong et al.* to their prior works in CTU/CU partitioning. In this regard, they moved towards the use of sum of absolute difference (SAD) costs in a two-layer ME to determine whether to split a CU or not, which shares some similarities with the algorithm proposed in this paper [35]. They also provided this algorithm with an early skip detection method based on the R-D costs obtained by the n previous CUs coded with this mode.

2.4. CTU/CU Splitting and Mode Decision

In the preceding subsections, it has been possible to see a progression towards greater time savings by integrating more elements in the fast encoding algorithms, such as fast prediction methods, or skip detection schemes. While the latter enable the omission of unnecessary evaluations, if the skip mode is not selected, then the encoder is required to check all the prediction modes. For this reason, many authors have proposed mode decision algorithms, which limit the number of PUs to be evaluated for a given CU.

In a similar way to the CTU/CU splitting algorithms of the previous subsection, the use of neighboring information is also very frequent. As an example, the algorithm proposed by *L. Shen et al.* carries out the splitting decision on the basis of spatial neighboring CTUs [36]. Additionally, they propose an early termination method based on motion homogeneity, the R-D costs and the skip mode. Based on this work, *Z. Liu et al.* proposed alternative uses of the neighboring information to predict the partitioning and the prediction mode [37, 38]. *J.-H. Lee et al.* introduced a scheme in which the splitting decision is based on the R-D cost of the parent CU and the cost of the CUs in the current depth, and also a PU decision algorithm driven by spatial and temporal parameters, and depth correlations [39]. The method proposed by *W. Zhao et al.* classifies the CTUs into simple, complex or medial, so that the first or the last depth levels can be skipped according to the information of temporal neighbors [40]. The selection of PUs is conducted based on the residual of the $2N \times 2N$ inter prediction, and a fast intra mode decision algorithm. Finally, *D. G. Fernández et al.* extended their work on spatial homogeneity to support mode selection [41, 42].

With regard to machine learning techniques, and continuing on from their previous work, *G. Corrêa et al.* proposed a method based on decision trees to early terminate CTU/CU splitting, PU selection and residual quadtree (RQT) generation [43]. Similarly, *I. Zupancic et al.* introduced a variation of the visiting order of the CUs, so that depending on the prediction of a Bayesian classification model, the processing is

performed top-down or bottom-up, using early termination and inter mode decision algorithms [44].

Alternative approaches include the algorithm proposed by *Y.-J. Ahn and D. Sim*, which is based on the costs of the square PUs [45]. First, in a top-down approach, the R-D cost of these blocks is calculated, and then, in a bottom-up fashion it is decided whether it is necessary to check the remaining sizes according to the accumulated cost of the child CUs. *X. Wu et al.* addressed CU, PU and TU selection as an optimal stopping problem driven by reward functions [46]. More recently, *Z. Yang et al.* based the early CU splitting algorithm and the PU decision on edge information, namely edge similarity and edge movement [47].

Finally, our previous work is also included in this category. On the basis of the motion information calculated in a pre-analysis stage, the entire partitioning is estimated for each CTU from a statistical point of view [8]. This enables the omission of the evaluation of CUs and PUs that are unlikely to provide good R-D results. However, this method is not able to adapt the encoding process to prediction misses, which results in undesired coding inefficiencies in some scenarios.

3. Proposed CTU/CU Splitting and Mode Decision Algorithm

As shown in the previous section, the existing works on fast encoding make use of diverse techniques to reduce the encoding time, such as machine learning, reuse of neighboring information, and feature extraction, among others. The method proposed in this paper, however, is based on the pre-analysis stage proposed in [8], which enables the obtaining of valuable information from the input sequence prior to the encoding. In particular, this stage, which is called look-ahead in the proposed scheme, calculates the motion information of the input sequence in a similar way to the normal encoding process. The resulting inter prediction information is then used to estimate the optimal quadtree partitioning, and to guide the encoding through the mode decision process in an adaptive way. As a consequence, the total encoding time is notably reduced.

This model offers two major advantages in comparison with other schemes. Firstly, the similarities between the operations performed in the two stages result in a more optimal decision-making process when predicting the encoding decisions from the information obtained in the look-ahead stage. Secondly, the estimated motion information can be used, at no additional cost, for different purposes, such as rate control, scene change detection, bit allocation, perceptual coding or, as is the case for the proposed algorithm, acceleration of the encoding process.

The proposed scheme is thus divided into two stages: the look-ahead and the encoding itself. Both steps are described in detail in the following subsections.

3.1. Look-Ahead Stage

The main aim of the look-ahead stage is to obtain the inter prediction information used to guide the CTU/CU splitting and mode decision processes. To this end, this stage needs to perform an ME that is similar to the inter prediction module of

Figure 3: Diagram of the ME performed by the look-ahead stage.

the encoder. Nevertheless, given that the look-ahead stage only needs to provide an estimate of the motion in a frame, its design can be notably simpler than the normal ME.

Evaluating all the possible partitions defined in HEVC would be excessively time-consuming. For this reason, the look-ahead stage is restricted to square blocks: 8×8 , 16×16 , 32×32 , and 64×64 . This provides great flexibility when estimating the motion information in a frame. In this regard, the ME is carried out for each block size and on every reference frame, as depicted in Fig. 3, resulting in a data structure that stores the distortion value in terms of the SAD of each tuple. This same information is the one used later by the encoder to aid the splitting and mode decisions.

With the aim of obtaining the most reliable cost map possible, certain considerations were taken into account in the design of the look-ahead stage:

- The same search algorithm is used in both the look-ahead stage and the inter prediction module of the encoder. In this way, it is more likely that the two stages predict similar motion information. Nevertheless, given that the look-ahead stage is required to provide only an estimate of the costs, the precision of the search is limited to integer-pel samples instead of performing the full quarter-pel search, resulting in a faster estimation.
- The advanced motion vector prediction (AMVP) feature of the HEVC standard is assimilated in the look-ahead stage in such a way that the MVs of adjacent blocks are used as predictors. In this way, the MVs of the blocks above the current one and the one to the left are retrieved and used as predictors. If any of these are not available, a temporal candidate is used instead. If the number of available predictors after this selection process is lower than two, the list is filled with zero MVs, $(0, 0)$. To determine which predictor is finally used in the ME, both candidates are evaluated to select the one providing the lowest distortion.
- The following Lagrangian multiplier R-D optimization model is used:

$$J(MV) = Dist(MV) + \lambda \cdot Rate(MV), \quad (1)$$

where J represents the cost function for a given MV, $Dist$ the distortion function in terms of SAD, λ is the Lagrangian multiplier, and $Rate$ represents the function to calculate the bits required to code the MV. It should be noted that the rate is dependent on the previously selected predictor.

3.2. CTU/CU Partitioning and Mode Decision Algorithm

With the motion information obtained in the look-ahead stage, the idea behind the proposed method is to calculate an estimate of the partitioning for P and B slices. In this way, the processing of CUs and PUs is started by evaluating the corresponding blocks at the leaves of the estimated partitioning tree. From this point, the evaluation is then conducted adaptively using a top-down approach, and then bottom-up, enabling the early termination of both the CTU/CU splitting and mode decision processes. In essence, the proposed approach is to first evaluate the partitioning that is most likely to provide the best R-D outcome, and then perform small adjustments according to the results obtained. I slices, in turn, follow the traditional encoding flow.

The estimated partitioning tree is built from the motion information of the look-ahead stage. From bottom to top, the decision of splitting or not splitting a CU is determined according to its corresponding estimated cost, and the sum of accumulated costs of lower depths. Beginning from the leaves at depth $D - 1$ to the top at depth 0, where $D \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ represents the maximum partitioning depth allowed by the encoder, costs are recursively grouped into fours. If the sum of the costs estimated for each child CU is lower than the cost of a given CU, then the CU will be split, as this provides better coding efficiency according to the look-ahead algorithm.

In order to obtain the most accurate estimation of the partitioning, it is necessary to define the cost function that will determine the splitting decision. Encoders typically take the splitting decision on the basis of both the rate component and the distortion, as shown in Eq. 1. In a similar way, the proposed algorithm makes use of the motion information provided by the look-ahead stage to predict such parameters. Considering that a CU can be identified within a CTU as $CU_{d,i}$, where $d \in [0, D - 1]$ is the depth of the CU, and $i \in [0, 4^d - 1]$ is the index of the CU in Z-order for depth d , its associated estimated cost $C_{d,i}$ can be defined as:

$$C_{d,i} = \min_{r \in [0, R-1]} \{Dist(MV_{d,i,r}) + \lambda \cdot Rate(MV_{d,i,r})\}, \quad (2)$$

where R is the number of reference frames for the CU, $MV_{d,i,r}$ is the MV of the co-located look-ahead block for $CU_{d,i}$ and reference frame r , $Dist$ corresponds to the distortion function in terms of SAD, λ is the Lagrangian multiplier, and $Rate$ represents the rate component calculated as the number of bits needed to code the MV with respect to the predictor used, and an estimation of the bits needed to encode both the reference list and the reference frame. As can be seen, the calculation of $C_{d,i}$ is modeled on Eq. 1. It should also be noted that the QP takes part in the cost function through λ , so that high QP values lead to a higher weight for the rate component, and therefore to a lower fragmentation.

Having established the estimated cost function for a given CU, it is also necessary to define the procedure to determine the optimal partitioning quadtree according to these costs. In this regard, starting from the smallest CUs at depth $D - 1$ to the largest CU at depth 0, the following criterion is followed:

Figure 4: Estimation of the CTU/CU partitioning quadtree following a bottom-up approach.

$$S(CU_{d,i}) = \begin{cases} \text{split,} & \text{if } \sum_{j=0}^3 C_{d+1,4i+j}^* < C_{d,i} \\ & \text{and } d < D - 1 \\ \text{no split,} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where S represents the partitioning decision, and C^* is the cost assigned to a CU once the splitting decision has been taken. This new cost is defined as follows:

$$C_{d,i}^* = \begin{cases} \min \left\{ \sum_{j=0}^3 C_{d+1,4i+j}^*, C_{d,i} \right\}, & \text{if } d < D - 1 \\ C_{d,i}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

In conclusion, the procedure defined by Eq. 3 and 4 enables the construction of the optimal partitioning quadtree on the basis of the look-ahead costs. An example of its application is shown in Fig. 4. As can be seen, the costs are recursively grouped into fours, from the smallest blocks to the largest one. The numbers shown in the figure are examples of the sum of the C^* costs assigned to the child CUs, and the C costs associated with the blocks, for the split and non-split CUs respectively. Blocks shaded in gray represent CUs whose partitioning has been determined by following this procedure, but these become irrelevant for understanding the figure.

The result of the proposed tree building algorithm is optimal from the point of view of the look-ahead costs. Nevertheless, the quadtree obtained might not necessarily match the one that the encoder would have selected after a full R-D optimization process on all the possible combinations. This may involve coding inefficiencies due to the increase in the number of bits needed to encode the CTUs. There are three main reasons for this mismatch. Firstly, the predictors calculated in the look-ahead stage are used to avoid drifted MVs, and to calculate the rate component in the cost function. However, these may differ from the ones finally used in the encoding, producing alternative MVs, and thus different distortion costs and rate values. Secondly, P and B slices can contain intra-predicted PUs. Nevertheless, the percentage of inter-predicted PUs is significantly greater than the intra-predicted ones in these types of slices, so

it is assumed that the partitioning can be accurately estimated from only the inter prediction costs. And finally, the proposed scheme makes use of $2N \times 2N$ blocks to predict the partitioning, but HEVC defines additional PU sizes.

One approach to reduce the total processing time would be restricting the encoding to the partitioning defined by the estimated quadtree. Nevertheless, this would also lead to coding inefficiencies due to the mismatching issues enumerated above. For this reason, a safer approach has been considered for the proposed algorithm. In particular, the encoder adaptively evaluates CUs and PUs in higher and lower depth levels if certain conditions are met, which helps find the optimal prediction, and thus improve the coding efficiency.

The proposed scheme performs a recursive evaluation of the CTU, starting from depth 0 and subsequently splitting the CUs until it is decided to terminate the process early, or the maximum depth is reached. However, the evaluation of some CUs is temporarily omitted in this first top-down pass. In particular, the evaluation of all the CUs above the leaves of the estimated quadtree is postponed until a second bottom-up pass is performed. In this way, the first pass processes the CUs that were predicted as non-split by the proposed algorithm, allowing the evaluation of their child CUs only if the early termination condition is not met, whereas the second pass processes the corresponding parent CUs on the basis of the encoding information from the first pass. As a result, this processing order enables the evaluation of the partitioning and prediction modes that are most likely to provide the best coding efficiency at an early stage, while it also provides the encoder with the adaptivity to check additional modes. This scheme is depicted in Fig. 5.

The splitting and mode decisions are taken by the coded block flag (CBF). This flag accounts for the significance of the entire TU, i.e. it signals whether a TU contains non-zero transform coefficients [48]. Accordingly, it is possible to assume that there is a direct relationship between the splitting of a CU and the CBF. In this regard, assuming that the optimal prediction mode has a similar size to the leaf CU of the estimated quadtree, the approach followed in the top-down evaluation is to check modes from larger to smaller sizes, where the CBF acts as the stopping condition for both the mode decision and CTU/CU splitting, as shown in the left-side branch of Fig. 5. As a particular case, the first modes to be checked are the $2N \times 2N$ inter prediction and skip, for which an early skip detection (ESD) condition is defined instead. The ESD condition not only relies on the CBF, but it also checks whether the motion vector difference (MVD) for these modes is zero, as proposed by *J. Yang et al.* [49]. If the CBF is set, and the skip mode is selected or the MVD is zero, then the remaining modes are omitted and the splitting is terminated early.

The approach followed in the bottom-up evaluation is also based on the use of the CBF and the ESD condition. Nevertheless, the most significant difference with respect to the top-down pass is that the encoding information of the child CUs is available. As a result, it is possible to omit certain PUs on the basis of their encoding decisions. In particular, the $2N \times 2N$, $2N \times N$ and $N \times 2N$ inter prediction modes cover the same area as

Figure 5: Proposed guided evaluation performed by the encoder on the basis of the estimated quadtree.

all or some of these child CUs, and they also match their edges. For this reason, it is straightforward to consider that if the child CUs were split, then this region of the picture would not be homogeneous and then these modes would not be adequate, as they would increase the number of bits necessary to encode the residual. In this way, Fig. 5 shows in its right-side branch how these three symmetric modes are skipped if at least one of the child CUs is split.

Finally, it is worth pointing out the fast encoding methods that the encoder implements with regard to the asymmetric motion partitioning (AMP) modes: $2N \times nU$, $2N \times nD$, $nL \times 2N$ and

Algorithm 1 Top-down evaluation of AMP modes.

Input: size: current CU size
mode_{cur}: best candidate mode of the current CU
mode_{par}: best candidate mode of the parent CU

if size < 64×64 **and** mode_{par} != $2N \times 2N$ **then**
if mode_{cur} == $2N \times 2N$ no merge **or** mode_{par} == AMP **then**
Set $nL \times 2N$, $nR \times 2N$, $2N \times nU$ and $2N \times nD$ modes for evaluation
else if mode_{cur} == $2N \times N$ **then**
Set $2N \times nU$ and $2N \times nD$ modes for evaluation
else if mode_{cur} == $N \times 2N$ **then**
Set $nL \times 2N$ and $nR \times 2N$ modes for evaluation
else if mode_{cur} == $2N \times 2N$ no skip **or** mode_{par} == AMP **then**
Set $nL \times 2N$, $nR \times 2N$, $2N \times nU$ and $2N \times nD$ merge modes for evaluation
else if mode_{par} == intra **then**
if mode_{cur} == $N \times 2N$ **then**
Set $nL \times 2N$ and $nR \times 2N$ merge modes for evaluation
else if mode_{cur} == $2N \times N$ **then**
Set $2N \times nU$ and $2N \times nD$ merge modes for evaluation

Algorithm 2 Bottom-up evaluation of AMP modes.

Input: size: current CU size
subCU[4]: references to child CUs (0: top-left, 1: top-right, 2: bottom-left, and 3: bottom-right)
mode_{cur}: best candidate mode of the current CU

if size < 64×64 **then**
if mode_{cur} == $2N \times 2N$ no merge **then**
Set $nL \times 2N$, $nR \times 2N$, $2N \times nU$ and $2N \times nD$ modes for evaluation
else if mode_{cur} is not set **or** mode_{cur} == $2N \times N$ **then**
if subCU[0] is split **and** subCU[1] is split **then**
Set $2N \times nD$ mode for evaluation
if subCU[2] is split **and** subCU[3] is split **then**
Set $2N \times nU$ mode for evaluation
else if mode_{cur} is not set **or** mode_{cur} == $N \times 2N$ **then**
if subCU[0] is split **and** subCU[2] is split **then**
Set $nR \times 2N$ mode for evaluation
if subCU[1] is split **and** subCU[3] is split **then**
Set $nL \times 2N$ mode for evaluation
if mode_{cur} == $2N \times 2N$ no skip **then**
Set $nL \times 2N$, $nR \times 2N$, $2N \times nU$ and $2N \times nD$ merge modes for evaluation

$nR \times 2N$. To reduce the complexity of the encoding, some of these modes are omitted. In particular, the omission of modes in the top-down evaluation is based on the prediction mode selected for both the current CU and the parent CU [50]. By contrast, the bottom-up evaluation takes into account the splitting decision of the child CUs in addition to the mode selected for the current CU. Both approaches are depicted in Algorithms 1 and 2, respectively.

3.3. Integration With Other Fast Encoding Methods Based on a Look-Ahead Stage

As mentioned above, one of the most significant advantages of the proposed method is that the information calculated in the look-ahead stage can be used in the encoder for other purposes. In previous works, we utilized the motion information of this preliminary stage to accelerate inter prediction [51, 52]. The aim of the algorithm in those works was thus the same as in this paper, i.e. to reduce the total encoding time. However, that approach is completely different from the splitting and mode decision algorithm proposed in this paper. Firstly, the distortion costs were used to delimit the set of reference frames used for prediction for each PU. Secondly, the estimated MVs were

Table 1: Per-Sequence Results of the Proposed CTU/CU Splitting Algorithm

Class	Video sequence	Random Access		Low Delay P		Low Delay B	
		BD-rate (%)	TR (%)	BD-rate (%)	TR (%)	BD-rate (%)	TR (%)
A	Traffic	0.19	50.64	0.24	43.19	0.35	44.07
	PeopleOnStreet	0.43	22.82	0.40	17.10	0.45	18.27
B	Kimono	0.16	39.79	0.29	30.41	0.28	31.39
	ParkScene	0.24	47.52	0.50	37.92	0.46	38.54
	Cactus	0.37	41.48	0.82	33.33	0.60	35.24
	BasketballDrive	0.26	37.61	0.29	28.48	0.28	30.42
	BQTerrace	0.51	48.93	1.07	40.99	0.42	42.14
C	BasketballDrill	0.27	32.76	0.27	24.86	0.23	26.43
	BQMall	0.35	39.03	0.55	31.43	0.55	33.07
	PartyScene	0.36	29.81	0.38	23.22	0.38	23.64
	RaceHorses	0.50	23.57	0.35	16.61	0.36	16.96
D	BasketballPass	0.54	26.89	0.63	21.08	0.56	22.37
	BQSquare	0.27	37.21	0.61	29.56	0.46	29.19
	BlowingBubbles	0.32	33.16	0.51	27.18	0.59	28.12
	RaceHorses	0.48	21.84	0.47	16.01	0.56	16.82
E	FourPeople	0.12	62.50	0.52	57.91	0.49	58.43
	Johnny	0.23	67.67	0.80	63.71	0.81	63.57
	KristenAndSara	0.14	63.22	0.04	57.14	0.32	57.58
F	BasketballDrillText	0.26	32.12	0.44	25.00	0.30	26.04
	ChinaSpeed	1.06	26.84	0.78	19.63	0.70	21.55
	SlideEditing	0.05	76.44	0.29	73.14	-0.37	72.13
	SlideShow	0.72	63.62	0.86	57.95	0.61	59.67
Average (all sequences)		0.36	41.98	0.50	35.27	0.44	36.17

used as an accurate starting point for the ME, leading to a reduction of the search area, and thus of the number of SAD calculations. In the end, the time devoted to inter prediction was notably reduced, while coding efficiency was maintained.

In contrast to these earlier works, the algorithm proposed in this paper functions at the CTU/CU level. Therefore, the two approaches can work together with the aim of reducing the total encoding time to a greater extent by accelerating the splitting, the mode decision, and inter prediction. In this regard, the performance of the proposed method will be evaluated with, and without integration with the aforementioned works to assess the contribution of both approaches.

4. Experimental Evaluation

The experiments were executed on HM 16.6 [6], following the guidelines and coding conditions provided by the document elaborated by the JCT-VC [7]. In this regard, the QP values tested were 22, 27, 32 and 37, and the selected configurations were RA, low delay P (LDP), and low delay B (LDB). The encodings were carried out using the Main profile and 8-bit depth. Sequences of classes A to F according to the JCT-VC classification were used, which include the following resolutions: 2560×1600 (A), 1920×1080 (B), 832×480 (C and F), 416×240 (D), 1280×720 (E and F), and 1024×768 (F). Classes A to D comprise camera-view scene content, class E is composed of videoconferencing content, and class F consists of screen content (non-camera-captured and mixed imagery). A search area of 128×128 pixels was used for the look-ahead

stage, which is equivalent to the default search area for the baseline encoder.

The hardware platform used in the experiments was composed of an Intel® Xeon® E5-2630L v3 CPU running at 1.80 GHz. The encoder was compiled with GCC 4.8.5-4 and executed on CentOS 7 (Linux 3.10.0-327). Turbo Boost was disabled to ensure the reproducibility of the results.

The results are given in terms of time reduction (TR) and the Bjøntegaard delta rate (BD-rate). The BD-rate is a measure of coding efficiency that represents the percentage of bitrate variation between two sequences with the same objective quality [53]. Higher time reduction and lower BD-rate values represent better results.

First, the results of the CTU/CU splitting and mode decision algorithms will be shown individually to assess their contribution to the proposed method. In this regard, Tables 1 and 2 show the average TR for the four QP values and the BD-rate for each test sequence and coding configuration. As can be seen, the RA configuration obtains better coding efficiency results and higher time savings on average than the other two configurations. This can be attributed to the coding pattern used in RA compared with the low-delay configurations, which potentially results in more distinct R-D values, and thus the splitting and mode decisions become easier to take. The results also show that the proposed CTU/CU splitting algorithm obtains significantly positive results for the three sequences of class E and *SlideEditing*. This is caused by the low motion displayed in these sequences, which leads to larger partitions, added to the ability of the algorithm to adapt the visiting order of the CUs.

Table 2: Per-Sequence Results of the Proposed Mode Decision Algorithm

Class	Video sequence	Random Access		Low Delay P		Low Delay B	
		BD-rate (%)	TR (%)	BD-rate (%)	TR (%)	BD-rate (%)	TR (%)
A	Traffic	1.32	54.32	1.54	50.71	1.79	51.16
	PeopleOnStreet	1.19	48.08	0.78	42.48	1.01	43.20
B	Kimono	1.61	44.41	1.50	37.69	1.43	37.86
	ParkScene	0.88	52.80	1.11	48.02	1.19	48.31
	Cactus	1.17	46.96	1.22	41.47	1.19	41.97
	BasketballDrive	1.66	44.16	1.11	37.64	1.29	38.76
	BQTerrace	1.46	52.20	1.74	49.03	1.86	47.87
C	BasketballDrill	0.91	44.49	0.58	38.24	0.59	38.96
	BQMall	1.20	50.76	1.04	45.20	1.03	46.09
	PartyScene	0.69	49.19	0.89	45.60	0.94	45.69
	RaceHorses	1.30	43.15	0.73	36.91	0.88	37.83
D	BasketballPass	0.94	45.62	0.71	39.98	0.83	41.52
	BQSquare	0.85	52.22	1.53	50.59	1.44	50.07
	BlowingBubbles	0.57	59.23	0.90	43.76	0.96	43.40
	RaceHorses	1.30	45.44	0.89	39.51	0.98	40.44
E	FourPeople	0.83	54.58	1.20	51.94	1.41	52.19
	Johnny	1.24	55.73	2.47	54.79	2.27	54.44
	KristenAndSara	1.29	53.98	1.96	51.26	1.97	51.17
F	BasketballDrillText	0.78	45.94	0.66	40.15	0.75	40.59
	ChinaSpeed	1.35	41.33	1.25	36.08	1.29	37.95
	SlideEditing	0.18	57.37	0.97	58.11	0.61	57.98
	SlideShow	1.09	53.19	1.33	50.78	1.23	52.18
Average (all sequences)		1.08	49.32	1.19	45.00	1.22	45.44

For the same reason, it is possible to observe a slightly higher TR for high-resolution sequences compared with those of lower resolution. With regard to the mode decision algorithm, similar TR results are obtained regardless of the sequence evaluated.

After the analysis of each approach separately, Table 3 shows the corresponding results of the overall algorithm. As can be seen, the conclusions drawn above also apply to these results. In this regard, sequences with larger CU sizes benefit from higher time savings. Moreover, it is important to note that the TR of the proposed algorithm is the result of the accumulated time savings of the two separate approaches. As a consequence, the TR can reach values of more than 86% at the expense of a very small increase in bitrate.

Another important aspect to take into account in the evaluation of the proposed method and the interpretation of the results above is the accuracy of the algorithm. In this regard, Tables 4 and 5 show the hit rate of both the CTU/CU splitting and mode decisions taken by the proposed algorithm in comparison with the baseline encoder, respectively. I slices were ignored in its calculation, given that they are encoded using the baseline algorithm. To provide a more accurate measurement of the accuracy, each CU is encoded twice, first using the original algorithm, and then using the proposed algorithm. As shown in the tables, the proposed method is able to successfully predict more than 96% of the CTU/CU splitting and mode decisions on average, which proves very significant, and is the reason for its excellent coding efficiency. On top of that, the achieved accuracy is homogeneous for the four QP values tested, which shows that the proposed algorithm adapts to this parameter adequately.

Figure 6: Profiling of the baseline (upper bar) compared with the proposed algorithm (lower bar) for each configuration.

In order to show the effect of the proposed algorithm on the encoder, Fig. 6 shows the profiling results obtained by the proposed algorithm compared with the baseline encoder. These timing values have been extracted from the average profiles of all the tested sequences and QP values for each encoding configuration. In this regard, the most important information to be extracted from the figure is the amount of time devoted to the look-ahead stage. As can be seen, this stage takes approximately 2–3% of the total encoding time (6–8% with respect to the encoding time of the proposal). Considering the time savings achieved, this amount of time proves negligible. It is worth

Table 3: Per-Sequence Results of the Proposed CTU/CU Splitting and Mode Decision Algorithm

Class	Video sequence	Random Access		Low Delay P		Low Delay B	
		BD-rate (%)	TR (%)	BD-rate (%)	TR (%)	BD-rate (%)	TR (%)
A	Traffic	1.20	73.41	1.66	66.15	1.90	68.22
	PeopleOnStreet	1.76	55.66	1.29	47.86	1.50	50.00
B	Kimono	1.54	60.24	1.55	49.56	1.50	51.64
	ParkScene	1.06	70.53	1.63	61.38	1.55	63.38
	Cactus	1.52	63.07	2.18	53.68	1.87	56.53
	BasketballDrive	1.70	58.87	1.33	48.82	1.45	51.74
	BQTerrace	1.91	70.15	2.76	62.86	1.99	63.91
C	BasketballDrill	1.10	56.71	1.05	47.19	1.07	49.84
	BQMall	1.55	65.44	1.61	56.32	1.72	59.04
	PartyScene	1.14	59.75	1.47	52.05	1.34	54.02
	RaceHorses	1.90	51.93	1.18	43.23	1.26	45.40
D	BasketballPass	1.50	55.19	1.48	47.27	1.48	50.06
	BQSquare	1.22	65.92	2.21	59.39	1.77	60.59
	BlowingBubbles	1.05	61.00	1.67	51.97	1.64	53.88
	RaceHorses	1.87	52.83	1.41	44.61	1.63	46.58
E	FourPeople	0.74	79.94	1.51	73.62	1.90	75.63
	Johnny	0.94	82.60	2.52	78.29	2.35	79.68
	KristenAndSara	0.91	79.42	1.45	72.68	1.63	74.40
F	BasketballDrillText	1.08	57.60	0.96	48.67	1.10	50.82
	ChinaSpeed	2.31	51.65	1.88	43.40	1.91	46.64
	SlideEditing	0.21	86.79	0.75	85.69	0.25	86.89
	SlideShow	1.55	78.48	1.61	73.24	1.64	76.44
Average (all sequences)		1.35	65.33	1.60	57.63	1.57	59.79

Table 4: Hit Rate of the Proposed CTU/CU Splitting Decision Algorithm Compared With HM (in %)

Class	Random Access				Low Delay P				Low Delay B			
	QP 22	QP 27	QP 32	QP 37	QP 22	QP 27	QP 32	QP 37	QP 22	QP 27	QP 32	QP 37
A	94.68	94.77	95.14	95.70	95.17	94.85	94.81	95.20	95.82	95.01	94.84	95.27
B	95.37	96.29	96.94	97.54	95.19	95.57	96.07	96.80	96.06	96.20	96.53	97.24
C	96.00	95.51	95.25	95.41	96.35	95.35	95.13	95.06	96.42	95.82	95.38	95.27
D	95.59	95.00	95.09	95.59	95.59	93.73	93.59	94.16	95.74	94.25	94.15	94.57
E	96.12	97.37	97.99	98.51	95.26	96.05	96.87	97.82	95.70	96.36	97.15	98.04
F	97.25	97.07	96.96	97.13	97.65	97.47	97.15	97.17	97.68	97.46	97.19	97.21
Average	95.90	96.06	96.28	96.69	95.93	95.54	95.64	96.07	96.29	95.92	95.94	96.32

Table 5: Hit Rate of the Proposed Mode Decision Algorithm Compared With HM (in %)

Class	Random Access				Low Delay P				Low Delay B			
	QP 22	QP 27	QP 32	QP 37	QP 22	QP 27	QP 32	QP 37	QP 22	QP 27	QP 32	QP 37
A	95.51	94.87	94.76	95.24	96.58	95.62	95.10	95.26	96.50	95.51	95.08	95.32
B	96.74	96.56	96.74	97.25	96.99	96.84	96.84	97.30	97.38	97.07	97.08	97.58
C	96.24	95.39	94.87	95.07	97.11	96.28	95.63	95.53	96.96	96.21	95.59	95.59
D	96.10	95.07	94.69	94.91	97.01	95.49	94.79	94.82	96.69	95.32	94.73	94.91
E	97.34	97.16	97.32	97.88	97.43	97.10	97.19	97.81	97.46	97.14	97.32	98.00
F	96.92	96.73	96.60	96.78	97.63	97.47	97.27	97.29	97.52	97.38	97.18	97.26
Average	96.54	96.04	95.90	96.25	97.16	96.53	96.21	96.41	97.13	96.52	96.25	96.53

noting also that the information calculated in the look-ahead stage can be reused for other purposes without increasing the complexity of this stage.

An illustrative comparison between the baseline encoding and the one performed by the proposed algorithm is shown in Fig. 7. This figure displays the partitioning performed by the

Figure 7: Comparison of the CTU/CU and PU partitioning between the baseline encoder and the proposed approach.

Table 6: Results of the Integration of the Proposed Algorithm With [51, 52]

Configuration	Prior Work [51, 52]		Proposed + [51, 52]	
	BD-rate (%)	TR (%)	BD-rate (%)	TR (%)
Random Access	0.55	18.36	1.83	70.55
Low Delay P	0.55	21.17	2.09	65.93
Low Delay B	0.79	22.95	2.32	68.20

two alternatives of the 104th frame of the *ParkScene* sequence for the RA configuration with two different QPs. As can be seen, the two methods are able to adapt the partitioning to the features of the picture. In this regard, it should be noted that even though the difference in the splitting and mode decisions can be caused by the omission of some of the CUs and PUs by the proposed method, they can also differ because these new decisions become optimal in terms of R-D.

On average, the TR obtained by the proposed CTU/CU algorithm reaches 65.33%, which is almost two thirds of the total encoding time, while the low-delay configurations range from 57.63% to 59.79%. The increase in bitrate is, in turn, negligible, not exceeding 1.60% on average. As analyzed above, the proposed scheme obtains significant TRs for low-motion sequences, and also high-resolution video, which is the main target of HEVC, thus representing an excellent solution for this new generation of video coding.

As mentioned in Section 3.3, the proposed scheme can be combined with other fast encoding algorithms. In particular, the motion information calculated in the look-ahead stage can be used to further accelerate the encoding, such as when using the fast inter prediction algorithm proposed in our previous works [51, 52]. As a way to show the effects of this integration, the proposed splitting and mode decision algorithm has been

combined with this complementary algorithm with the aim of providing greater time savings. The average results of this integration are shown in Table 6. As can be seen, the fast inter prediction algorithm enables an additional TR of around 8% for the RA configuration, and approximately 14% for the low-delay configurations, with respect to that offered by the proposed algorithm, which is reflected in a very significant TR that is larger than 70% for RA. The impact in terms of BD-rate is still very low, not exceeding 2% for RA, which represents an excellent trade-off between time savings and coding efficiency.

5. Comparison With Related Works

In this section, the results obtained by the proposed algorithm are compared with those of other works that aim to omit the evaluation of CUs and PUs that are unlikely to provide optimal R-D results, and thus have a strong relationship with the method proposed in this paper. In this regard, our algorithm will be compared first with the fast encoding techniques implemented in HM, and then with the related works described in Section 2.

5.1. Fast Encoding Techniques in HM

The HM encoder implements three main early termination techniques, namely the early CU (ECU) termination technique proposed by *K. Choi et al.* [54], the ESD algorithm proposed by *J. Yang et al.* [49], and the CBF fast mode (CFM) introduced by *R.-H. Gweon et al.* [55]. The ECU technique terminates the CTU/CU partitioning process if the best mode found for a given CU is the skip mode. The ESD algorithm, in turn, relies on the encoding of the $2N \times 2N$ PU, and in particular on its CBF flag, and whether the skip mode is selected or the MVD is zero, to omit the evaluation of the remaining modes within a CU. Finally, CFM stops the evaluation of PUs within a CU as soon as the CBF flag is set to zero.

The three techniques were evaluated under the conditions established in Section 4, following the coding conditions provided by the JCT-VC in [7], and using the RA, LDP and LDB coding configurations. They were evaluated both separately to analyze the performance of each individual algorithm, and combined to determine the maximum performance achieved by HM using the default fast encoding techniques.

Table 7 shows the average results of the evaluation. As can be seen, each technique provides some time savings at the cost of small coding penalties, especially ECU and ESD. When combined, the achieved TR is higher, but the BD-rate also increases significantly. In the case of RA, it should be noted that the proposed algorithm outperforms the combination of the three algorithms in terms of both coding efficiency and TR. With respect to LDP and LDB, the time savings of the proposed algorithm are significantly greater than those of the default techniques, while the coding efficiency achieved by the latter is slightly higher. In general terms, however, the proposed algorithm outperforms the ECU, ESD and CFM techniques, both individually and collectively, from the point of view of the encoding time while offering good BD-rate results.

Table 7: Comparison With the Fast Encoding Techniques of HM

Config.	Algorithm	BD-rate (%)	TR (%)
Random Access	ECU [54]	0.44	43.63
	ESD [49]	0.27	36.39
	CFM [55]	0.92	41.57
	ECU [54] + ESD [49] + CFM [55]	1.84	56.06
	Proposed algorithm	1.35	65.33
	Proposed algorithm + [51, 52]	1.83	70.55
Low Delay P	ECU [54]	0.24	35.35
	ESD [49]	0.37	30.80
	CFM [55]	1.11	35.65
	ECU [54] + ESD [49] + CFM [55]	1.36	45.95
	Proposed algorithm	1.60	57.63
	Proposed algorithm + [51, 52]	2.09	65.93
Low Delay B	ECU [54]	0.16	35.74
	ESD [49]	0.32	31.02
	CFM [55]	1.04	36.76
	ECU [54] + ESD [49] + CFM [55]	1.18	47.74
	Proposed algorithm	1.57	59.79
	Proposed algorithm + [51, 52]	2.32	68.20

5.2. Related Works in the State of the Art

As seen in Section 2, there are numerous works in the state of the art regarding CTU/CU splitting and mode decisioning. In this subsection, the results of the proposed algorithm will be compared with those obtained by some of the related works. In this regard, the comparison will be performed with respect to the average BD-rate and TR values reported by the authors in their works, with the exception of the algorithm proposed by *M. Xu et al.* [23], whose code is publicly available for LDP configuration, and thus was evaluated under the coding conditions established in Section 4.

To ensure the comparability of the results, only the related works that strictly followed the coding conditions established by the JCT-VC in [7] were selected. Moreover, only the results of those proposals measured in versions greater or equal to HM 16.0 were used in the comparison, as it is the latest major release of the encoder at the moment of writing, and later versions of HM only included minor bug fixes. The results were rounded to the highest common precision of the values provided. The comparison was made for the three coding configurations: RA, LDP and LDB. Consequently, the same work may appear in more than one configuration.

Table 8 summarizes the results obtained by the related works using the RA configuration. These have been sorted according to their type and in ascending order of TR. The most significant conclusion that can be drawn from the table is that the proposed algorithm outperforms all the presented works in terms of TR. Moreover, the integration of our proposal with the fast inter prediction algorithm represents the fastest scheme among all. In terms of coding efficiency, some of the algorithms provide a slightly lower BD-rate, but at the expense of a notably lower TR. In particular, it is worth noting that the proposed method outperforms our previous work, *G. Cebrián et al.* [8], in terms of both coding efficiency and time reduction. This indicates

Table 8: Comparison With the Related Works (RA Configuration)

Type	Related Work	BD-rate (%)	TR (%)
CU	H.-L. Tan et al. [13]	1.2	45
	M. Grellert et al. [20]	0.5	48
CU+Skip	M. Tang et al. [32]	0.9	48
	J. Zhang et al. [34]	1.2	55
CU+PU	D. G. Fernández et al. [41]	1.1	29
	X. Wu et al. [46]	1.4	51
	Z. Yang et al. [47]	1.5	54
	G. Cebrián et al. [8]	3.4	63
	Proposed algorithm	1.4	65
	Proposed algorithm + [51, 52]	1.8	71

Table 9: Comparison With the Related Works (LDP Configuration)

Type	Related Work	BD-rate (%)	TR (%)
CU	M. Grellert et al. [20]	0.6	41
	J. Liu et al. [16]	1.6	41
	S. Momcilovic et al. [26]	1.2	48
	M. Xu et al. [23]	1.7	49
CU+Pred	T. Mallikarachchi et al. [30]	2.3	58
CU+Skip	J. Zhang et al. [34]	1.0	46
CU+PU	D. G. Fernández et al. [41]	0.9	29
	Proposed algorithm	1.6	58
	Proposed algorithm + [51, 52]	2.1	66

Table 10: Comparison With the Related Works (LDB Configuration)

Type	Related Work	BD-rate (%)	TR (%)
CU	M. Grellert et al. [20]	0.6	44
	H.-L. Tan et al. [13]	0.8	44
CU+Pred	T. Mallikarachchi et al. [30]	2.3	61
CU+Skip	M. Tang et al. [32]	0.7	48
CU+PU	Z. Yang et al. [47]	1.8	55
	Proposed algorithm	1.6	60
	Proposed algorithm + [51, 52]	2.3	68

that evaluating CUs and PUs in an adaptive way on the basis of the information provided by the look-ahead stage results in a significant improvement.

The results of the LDP and LDB configurations are presented in Tables 9 and 10, respectively. Once again, the proposed algorithm outperforms the majority of the related works in these configurations in terms of TR while offering good coding efficiency results. Although the machine learning algorithm presented by *T. Mallikarachchi et al.* [30] obtains similar time savings, it is visibly outperformed by our algorithm in terms of BD-rate. Other related works such as *Z. Yang et al.* [47] are outperformed in the two dimensions. The remaining works in the comparison obtain significantly lower TR results.

In summary, our proposed algorithm is among the fastest methods in the recent literature. In fact, its integration with the fast inter prediction algorithm achieves the highest TR for all the configurations. While some of the related works present slightly better coding efficiency, our algorithm displays a better trade-off between time savings and coding efficiency. As shown in Section 2, many of the works propose complex algorithms to accelerate CTU/CU splitting and the mode decision, such as machine learning techniques. Nevertheless, our method is able to outperform them by using much simpler methods. Additionally, unlike other algorithms whose applicability is limited to quadtree partitioning, the proposed algorithm obtains valuable information such as MVs and distortion costs, which can be used for other purposes, e.g. rate control and bit allocation.

6. Conclusions

Among all the coding tools introduced by HEVC, the new CTU-based partitioning scheme provides the flexibility that enables the greatest adaptability of the encoding to the intrinsic features of the sequence compared with its predecessors. Nevertheless, it also involves a huge increment in the computational complexity of the encoder, making it difficult to successfully implement this standard in real-world scenarios. For this reason, the main focus of this paper is on tackling this complexity. In this regard, we propose an adaptive CTU/CU partitioning and mode decision algorithm for P and B slices that is based on a look-ahead stage. In this stage, a preliminary ME is performed to obtain the motion information that is used as a basis for the estimation of the partitioning quadtree. This estimation enables the reordering of the evaluation in such a way that the CUs that are predicted as non-split are checked first. Later, the encoder may decide to evaluate CUs at higher or lower depth levels, or to early terminate the CTU. Moreover, some modes may be omitted on the basis of previous encoding decisions and results.

The proposed algorithm exploits the similarity between the look-ahead stage and the inter prediction to perform accurate predictions. In this regard, the experimental evaluation of the proposed adaptive scheme shows that it is able to reduce the encoding time by 65.33% for the RA configuration while maintaining the coding efficiency of the standard, with a negligible impact of a 1.35% BD-rate. Apart from the excellent trade-off provided, the proposed algorithm has two key advantages. Firstly, its simplicity compared with other methods, and secondly, the possibility of extending the algorithm by reusing the motion information from the look-ahead stage. As a way to show this, we also evaluated the integration of the proposed method with a fast inter prediction algorithm, showing that this aggregation can achieve a TR of 70.55% at the expense of only a 1.83% BD-rate for the RA configuration. The two methods were compared against the most relevant related works in the field, outperforming them in terms of TR, and thus offering a better trade-off between time savings and coding efficiency.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness and the European Commission (FEDER funds) under the project TIN2015-66972-C5-2-R, by the Regional Government of Castile-La Mancha under the project SBPLY/17/180501/000353, and by the Spanish Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports under the grant FPU13/04601.

References

- [1] ISO/IEC, ITU-T, High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC). ITU-T Recommendation H.265 and ISO/IEC 23008-2 (Apr. 2013).
- [2] ISO/IEC, ITU-T, Advanced Video Coding for Generic Audiovisual Services. ITU-T Recommendation H.264 and ISO/IEC 14496-10 (May 2003).
- [3] G. J. Sullivan, J.-R. Ohm, W.-J. Han, T. Wiegand, Overview of the High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) Standard, *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.* 22 (12) (2012) 1649–1668. doi:10.1109/TCSVT.2012.2221191.
- [4] J.-R. Ohm, G. J. Sullivan, H. Schwarz, T. K. Tan, T. Wiegand, Comparison of the Coding Efficiency of Video Coding Standards - Including High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC), *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.* 22 (12) (2012) 1669–1684. doi:10.1109/TCSVT.2012.2221192.
- [5] F. Bossen, B. Bross, K. Suhling, D. Flynn, HEVC Complexity and Implementation Analysis, *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.* 22 (12) (2012) 1685–1696. doi:10.1109/TCSVT.2012.2221255.
- [6] HEVC Test Model (HM) Reference Software, <https://hevc.hhi.fraunhofer.de/>.
- [7] F. Bossen, Common Test Conditions and Software Reference Configurations, Tech. Rep. JCTVC-L1100 (Jan. 2013).
- [8] G. Cebrián-Márquez, J. L. Martínez, P. Cuenca, A Motion-Based Partitioning Algorithm for HEVC Using a Pre-Analysis Stage, *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.* In press. doi:10.1109/TCSVT.2018.2839026.
- [9] Q. Zhang, J. Zhao, X. Huang, Y. Gan, A Fast and Efficient Coding Unit Size Decision Algorithm Based on Temporal and Spatial Correlation, *Optik - Int. J. Light Electron Optics* 126 (21) (2015) 2793–2798. doi:10.1016/j.ijleo.2015.07.026.
- [10] Z. Pan, S. Kwong, Y. Zhang, J. Lei, H. Yuan, Fast Coding Tree Unit Depth Decision for High Efficiency Video Coding, in: 2014 IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP), 2014, pp. 3214–3218. doi:10.1109/ICIP.2014.7025650.
- [11] Y. Gao, P. Liu, Y. Wu, K. Jia, Quadtree Degeneration for HEVC, *IEEE Trans. Multimedia* 18 (12) (2016) 2321–2330. doi:10.1109/TMM.2016.2598481.
- [12] T.-L. Lin, C.-C. Chou, Z. Liu, K.-H. Tung, HEVC Early Termination Methods for Optimal CU Decision Utilizing Encoding Residual Information, *J. Real-Time Image Process.* In press. doi:10.1007/s11554-016-0608-9.
- [13] H. L. Tan, C. C. Ko, S. Rahardja, Fast Coding Quad-Tree Decisions Using Prediction Residuals Statistics for High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC), *IEEE Trans. Broadcast.* 62 (1) (2016) 128–133. doi:10.1109/TBC.2015.2505406.
- [14] J. Xiong, H. Li, Q. Wu, F. Meng, A Fast HEVC Inter CU Selection Method Based on Pyramid Motion Divergence, *IEEE Trans. Multimedia* 16 (2) (2014) 559–564. doi:10.1109/TMM.2013.2291958.
- [15] J. Xiong, H. Li, F. Meng, S. Zhu, Q. Wu, B. Zeng, MRF-Based Fast HEVC Inter CU Decision With the Variance of Absolute Differences, *IEEE Trans. Multimedia* 16 (8) (2014) 2141–2153. doi:10.1109/TMM.2014.2356795.
- [16] J. Liu, H. Jia, G. Xiang, X. Huang, B. Cai, C. Zhu, D. Xie, An Adaptive Inter CU Depth Decision Algorithm for HEVC, in: 2015 Visual Communications and Image Processing (VCIP), 2015, pp. 322–325. doi:10.1109/VCIP.2015.7457873.
- [17] Y. Li, G. Yang, Y. Zhu, X. Ding, X. Sun, Adaptive Inter CU Depth Decision for HEVC Using Optimal Selection Model and En-

- coding Parameters, *IEEE Trans. Broadcast.* 63 (3) (2017) 535–546. doi:10.1109/TBC.2017.2704423.
- [18] D. G. Fernández, A. A. Del Barrio, G. Botella, C. García, Fast and Effective CU Size Decision Based on Spatial and Temporal Homogeneity Detection, *Multimed. Tools Appl.* 77 (5) (2018) 5907–5927. doi:10.1007/s11042-017-4503-6.
- [19] G. Corrêa, P. Assunção, L. Agostini, L. A. da Silva Cruz, Fast Coding Tree Structure Decision for HEVC Based on Classification Trees, *Analog Integr. Circ. Sig. Process.* 87 (2) (2016) 129–139. doi:10.1007/s10470-016-0719-z.
- [20] M. Grellert, B. Zatt, S. Bampi, L. A. da Silva Cruz, Fast Coding Unit Partition Decision for HEVC Using Support Vector Machines, *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.* In press. doi:10.1109/TCSVT.2018.2849941.
- [21] K. Kim, W. W. Ro, Fast CU Depth Decision for HEVC using Neural Networks, *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.* In press. doi:10.1109/TCSVT.2018.2839113.
- [22] Y. Zhang, S. Kwong, X. Wang, H. Yuan, Z. Pan, L. Xu, Machine Learning-Based Coding Unit Depth Decisions for Flexible Complexity Allocation in High Efficiency Video Coding, *IEEE Trans. Image Process.* 24 (7) (2015) 2225–2238. doi:10.1109/TIP.2015.2417498.
- [23] M. Xu, T. Li, Z. Wang, X. Deng, R. Yang, Z. Guan, Reducing Complexity of HEVC: A Deep Learning Approach, *IEEE Trans. Image Process.* 27 (10) (2018) 5044–5059. doi:10.1109/TIP.2018.2847035.
- [24] H.-S. Kim, R.-H. Park, Fast CU Partitioning Algorithm for HEVC Using an Online-Learning-Based Bayesian Decision Rule, *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.* 26 (1) (2016) 130–138. doi:10.1109/TCSVT.2015.2444672.
- [25] H. Amer, A. Rashwan, E.-h. Yang, Fully Connected Network for HEVC CU Split Decision Equipped with Laplacian Transparent Composite Model, in: 2018 Picture Coding Symposium (PCS), 2018, pp. 189–193. doi:10.1109/PCS.2018.8456290.
- [26] S. Momcilovic, N. Roma, L. Sousa, I. Milentijevic, Run-Time Machine Learning for HEVC/H.265 Fast Partitioning Decision, in: 2015 IEEE International Symposium on Multimedia (ISM), 2015, pp. 347–350. doi:10.1109/ISM.2015.70.
- [27] A. Jiménez-Moreno, E. Martínez-Enríquez, F. Díaz-de María, Complexity Control Based on a Fast Coding Unit Decision Method in the HEVC Video Coding Standard, *IEEE Trans. Multimedia* 18 (4) (2016) 563–575. doi:10.1109/TMM.2016.2524995.
- [28] S. Wang, F. Luo, S. Ma, X. Zhang, S. Wang, D. Zhao, W. Gao, Low Complexity Encoder Optimization for HEVC, *J. Visual Commun. Image Representation* 35 (Supplement C) (2016) 120–131. doi:10.1016/j.jvcir.2015.12.005.
- [29] H. Kibeya, F. Belghith, M. A. Ben Ayed, N. Masmoudi, Fast Coding Unit Selection and Motion Estimation Algorithm Based on Early Detection of Zero Block Quantified Transform Coefficients for High-Efficiency Video Coding Standard, *IET Image Process.* 10 (5) (2016) 371–380. doi:10.1049/iet-ipr.2015.0381.
- [30] T. Mallikarachi, D. S. Talagala, H. K. Arachchi, A. Fernando, Content-Adaptive Feature-Based CU Size Prediction for Fast Low-Delay Video Encoding in HEVC, *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.* 28 (3) (2018) 693–705. doi:10.1109/TCSVT.2016.2619499.
- [31] S. Ahn, B. Lee, M. Kim, A Novel Fast CU Encoding Scheme Based on Spatiotemporal Encoding Parameters for HEVC Inter Coding, *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.* 25 (3) (2015) 422–435. doi:10.1109/TCSVT.2014.2360031.
- [32] M. Tang, X. Chen, J. Gu, Y. Han, J. Wen, S. Yang, Accelerating HEVC Encoding Using Early-Split, *IEEE Signal Process. Lett.* 25 (2) (2018) 209–213. doi:10.1109/LSP.2017.2718184.
- [33] J. Lee, S. Kim, K. Lim, S. Lee, A Fast CU Size Decision Algorithm for HEVC, *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.* 25 (3) (2015) 411–421. doi:10.1109/TCSVT.2014.2339612.
- [34] J. Zhang, S. Kwong, X. Wang, Two-Stage Fast Inter CU Decision for HEVC Based on Bayesian Method and Conditional Random Fields, *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.* doi:10.1109/TCSVT.2017.2747618.
- [35] J. Xiong, H. Li, F. Meng, Q. Wu, K. N. Ngan, Fast HEVC Inter CU Decision Based on Latent SAD Estimation, *IEEE Trans. Multimedia* 17 (12) (2015) 2147–2159. doi:10.1109/TMM.2015.2491018.
- [36] L. Shen, Z. Liu, X. Zhang, W. Zhao, Z. Zhang, An Effective CU Size Decision Method for HEVC Encoders, *IEEE Trans. Multimedia* 15 (2) (2013) 465–470. doi:10.1109/TMM.2012.2231060.
- [37] Z. Liu, T.-L. Lin, C.-C. Chou, HEVC Coding-Unit Decision Algorithm Using Tree-Block Classification and Statistical Data Analysis, *Multimed. Tools Appl.* 76 (6) (2017) 9051–9072. doi:10.1007/s11042-016-3530-z.
- [38] Z. Liu, T.-L. Lin, C.-C. Chou, Efficient prediction of CU depth and PU mode for fast HEVC encoding using statistical analysis, *J. Visual Commun. Image Representation* 38 (Supplement C) (2016) 474–486. doi:10.1016/j.jvcir.2016.03.025.
- [39] J.-H. Lee, K. Goswami, B.-G. Kim, S. Jeong, J. S. Choi, Fast Encoding Algorithm for High-Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) System Based on Spatio-Temporal Correlation, *J. Real-Time Image Process.* 12 (2) (2016) 407–418. doi:10.1007/s11554-014-0484-0.
- [40] W. Zhao, T. Onoye, T. Song, Hierarchical Structure-Based Fast Mode Decision for H.265/HEVC, *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.* 25 (10) (2015) 1651–1664. doi:10.1109/TCSVT.2015.2395751.
- [41] D. G. Fernández, A. A. Del Barrio, G. Botella, C. García, M. Prieto-Matías, R. Hermida, Complexity Reduction in the HEVC/H265 Standard Based on Smooth Region Classification, *Digit. Signal Process.* 73 (2018) 24–39. doi:10.1016/j.dsp.2017.11.001.
- [42] D. G. Fernández, G. Botella, A. A. Del Barrio, C. García, M. Prieto-Matías, C. Grecos, HEVC Optimization Based on Human Perception for Real-Time Environments, *Multimed. Tools Appl.* In press. doi:10.1007/s11042-018-7033-y.
- [43] G. Corrêa, P. Assunção, L. V. Agostini, L. A. da Silva Cruz, Fast HEVC Encoding Decisions Using Data Mining, *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.* 25 (4) (2015) 660–673. doi:10.1109/TCSVT.2014.2363753.
- [44] I. Zupancic, S. G. Blasi, E. Peixoto, E. Izquierdo, Inter-Prediction Optimizations for Video Coding Using Adaptive Coding Unit Visiting Order, *IEEE Trans. Multimedia* 18 (9) (2016) 1677–1690. doi:10.1109/TMM.2016.2579505.
- [45] Y.-J. Ahn, D. Sim, Square-Type-First Inter-CU Tree Search Algorithm for Acceleration of HEVC Encoder, *J. Real-Time Image Process.* 12 (2) (2016) 419–432. doi:10.1007/s11554-015-0487-5.
- [46] X. Wu, H. Wang, Z. Wei, Optimal Stopping Theory Based Fast Coding Tree Unit Decision for High Efficiency Video Coding, in: 2016 Visual Communications and Image Processing (VCIP), 2016, pp. 101–104. doi:10.1109/VCIP.2016.7805450.
- [47] Z. Yang, S. Guo, Q. Shao, A Fast Inter-Frame Encoding Scheme Using the Edge Information and the Spatiotemporal Encoding Parameters for HEVC, *Multimed. Tools Appl.* 76 (22) (2017) 24125–24142. doi:10.1007/s11042-016-4165-9.
- [48] J. Sole, R. Joshi, N. Nguyen, T. Ji, M. Karczewicz, G. Clare, F. Henry, A. Dueñas, Transform Coefficient Coding in HEVC, *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.* 22 (12) (2012) 1765–1777. doi:10.1109/TCSVT.2012.2223055.
- [49] J. Yang, J. Kim, K. Won, H. Lee, B. Jeon, Early SKIP Detection for HEVC, *Tech. Rep. JCTVC-G543* (Nov. 2011).
- [50] C. Rosewarne, B. Bross, M. Naccari, K. Sharman, G. J. Sullivan, High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) Test Model 16. Improved Encoder Description Update 6, *Tech. Rep. JCTVC-X1002* (Jun. 2016).
- [51] G. Cebrián-Márquez, J. L. Martínez, P. Cuenca, A Pre-Analysis Algorithm for Fast Motion Estimation in HEVC, in: IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP), 2016, pp. 2013–2017. doi:10.1109/ICIP.2016.7532711.
- [52] G. Cebrián-Márquez, J. L. Martínez, P. Cuenca, Inter and Intra Pre-Analysis Algorithm for HEVC, *J. Supercomput.* 73 (1) (2017) 414–432. doi:10.1007/s11227-016-1882-9.
- [53] G. Bjøntegaard, Calculation of average PSNR differences between RD-curves, *Tech. Rep. VCEG-M33*, ITU-T Video Coding Experts Group (VCEG) (Mar. 2001).
- [54] K. Choi, S.-H. Park, E. S. Jang, Coding Tree Pruning Based CU Early Termination, *Tech. Rep. JCTVC-F092* (Jul. 2011).
- [55] R.-H. Gweon, Y.-L. Lee, J. Lim, Early Termination of CU Encoding to Reduce HEVC Complexity, *Tech. Rep. JCTVC-F045* (Jul. 2011).